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NATIONAL SERVICE TRAINING PROGRAM PRACTICES AND CHALLENGES OF TERTIARY EDUCATION IN TARLAC: BASIS FOR A PROPOSE TRAINING MANAGEMENT PLAN

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ABSTRACT

Title : NATIONAL SERVICE TRAINING PROGRAM PRACTICES
AND CHALLENGES OF TERTIARY EDUCATION IN TARLAC: BASIS FOR
A PROPOSE TRAINING MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Degree : Master Of Arts in Education

Major : Educational Management

The study aimed to evaluate the practices and challenges of national service training programs in private higher educational institutions and universities in Tarlac province. To gather data, descriptive research design was used. Questionnaire were given to the respondents. To interpret gathered data, frequency counts and percentages was used to determine the counts of the profile and the challenges of NSTP trainers. While mean in the other hand was used to describe the practices in NSTP.

Findings revealed that most of the institution particularly private school don't undergo orientation particularly about NSTP Act of 2001 or RA 9163. It was also revealed that providing basic information such as title, subject number, credit hours, subject policies in NSTP syllabus are very important. Also, used of lecture and showing in teaching CWTS are the number methods and strategies prepared by the CWTS faculty. Used of discussion-based in the other hand are the number one prepared teaching methods in teaching LTS.

Furthermore, results also revealed that the used of demonstration in assessing the performance of the students were the number one assessment tools prepared by the CWTS faculty while written works and activities and performance task for the LTS.

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Challenges met by both LTS and CWTS in private higher educational institution were lack of provisions for trainings and seminars, attitudes and behaviors of the students and lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds. Lack of facilities, equipment and supplies that may be used in teaching, large number of students, and no clear direction for the organization and mobilization of NSTP graduates are the top three challenges encountered by the universities.

Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that schools should have a standard orientations and training for NSTP instructors or facilitators from the office of the civil defense, commission on higher education and any government agencies related to NSTP. Also, school administration may hire additional faculty since some institution has only 1 faculty handling a huge number of students, NSTP Director with the help of NSTP coordinator should conduct a monthly or quarterly monitoring and evaluation for NSTP faculty and NSTP activities, NSTP Implementers and Directors should work on the creation of handbooks or modules to have standardized lessons in teaching NSTP. NSTP unit/office with the help of school administrator should establish a memorandum of agreement between schools and communities for the deployment of NSTP graduates.

The management plan proposed by the researcher based on the result of the study will help NSTP trainers, implementers and school administrators to have a better practices and management in NSTP (National Service Training Program)

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEMS AND ITS BACKGROUND

Background of the Study

"The best way to find yourself is to lose yourself in the service of others". It was July 23, 2001, since the RA 9163 or the NSTP Act of 2001 was enacted in response to public clamour for reforms in the Reserved Officers Training Corps (ROTC) Program. National Service Training program was designed to train students on how to strengthen their civic and community engagement and responsibilities. For them to know the importance and value of volunteering and losing their selves in the service of others. In the pursuit of these goals, the youth shall be motivated, trained, organized, and mobilized in military training (ROTC), literacy (LTS), civic welfare (CWTS), and other similar endeavours in service to the nation.

National service does not simply mean "serving the public"; it means serving the public under political and economic institutions; it means serving the nation in an age of nationalism; and it means constructing the nationalism which it serves (Gorham). These national services may be in the form of military, non-military services, non-military compulsory programs, and some even integrated in the educational system like in the Philippines in the form of the National Service Training Program (NSTP). These kinds of national services, which are integrated with the respective educational systems of each

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country, are forms of service-learning. That is why, in line with the act, students, male and female, of any baccalaureate degree course or at least two (2)-year technical-vocational courses in public and private educational institutions shall be required to complete one (1) of the NSTP components (its either Literacy Training Service, Civic Welfare Training Service or Reserve Officers' Training Corps) as requisite for graduation.

Reserve-Officers' Training Corps (ROTC) under the section 38 of the republic act 7077, is a program designed to provide military training to tertiary level students in order to motivate, train, organize and mobilize them for national defense preparedness. In the other hand, Literacy Training Service (LTS) is a component of NSTP that focuses on training students to become teachers of reading-writing literacy and numeracy to children, out-of-school youth, and other segments of society. Education students are primary target of this component, but other students from other colleges are equally encouraged to choose it. Teaching unprivileged segments of society which did not get formal education is a great way to be of help in building our nation while Civic Welfare training service is geared towards activities that have social impact through activities that could contribute to "health, education, environment, entrepreneurship, safety, recreation and morals of the citizenry", thus the CWTS component of the NSTP stressed the importance of youth involvement in broad programs or activities that will benefit the people. Both LTS and CWTS is a program designed to train students to strengthen the civic and community responsibilities of the students. It is the form of service learning.

Service-learning is an educational approach that combines learning objectives with community service in order to provide a pragmatic, progressive learning experience while meeting societal needs. Meaning, students learn inside the classroom to the real-world context in order to concretize learning and to strengthen civic and community responsibilities. Service learning is about hands-on participation in community-based projects. As what have Dale's Cone of Experience stated, learners retain more information by what they "do" as opposed to what is "heard", "read" or "observed. The most effective training involves direct experiences, such as hands-on or field experiences since experience has a greater influence or impact on the lives of the students. Having an effective training management towards students in conducting NSTP classes is very important. Effective training management can enhance their civic consciousness and it can develop their ethics of service and patriotism.

In Tarlac State University, before allowing the students to transfer on their chosen component, faculties are going to discuss first in NSTP 1 the common module which compose of 25 training hours which mainly focuses on the five (5) topics mentioned in the Rule III of RA 9163. That is why during this phase, the students have no specific component yet and are expected to gain knowledge, skills, and attitude towards deepened understanding and heightened appreciation of their role in the promotion of common good and the general welfare. Also, they are expected to demonstrate learning by applying concepts and principles on practical situations in pursuit of community development for the task of nation building.

Meanwhile, the specific modules shall be taken by the students after completing the Common Module phase and for a period equivalent to 29 hours to satisfy the minimum

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requirement as to training hours for NSTP 1 which is 54 hours. The modular topics covered herein are designed to help the students acknowledge their roles in the society they belong especially in engaging themselves to activities contributory to the general welfare as what the components are intended to.

In the other hand, NSTP 2 topics will help the students acknowledge their roles in the society they belong especially in engaging themselves to activities contributory the general welfare as what the components are intended to. In this phase, students are being introduced to the community-based activities as preparation of their involvement to the National Service Reserve Corps (NSRC) which they will be part of when they completed the NSTP. The NSRC is an organization composed of graduates of the CWTS and LTS components tasked to provide a trained, motivated, and organized manpower reservethat can be tapped by the State for DRRM, civic welfare, literacy, national emergency, environment protection and other similar endeavors in the service of the nation.

It was also reported in the Philippine daily inquirer that our country which is the Philippines are one of the corrupt countries in the world even though we claim to be the only Christian nation in Asia and people are very religious. And because of that, a person must go through a progression of transformation in converting himself with dignity aligned with the Filipino value. Thus, the CHED in partnership with Good Citizenship Movement published module on Good Citizenship Values emphasizing the role of 'Pagkamaka-Diyos' as the key and the core to good citizenship which is one of the topics covered during the common module that the NSTP students need to know and practice. But according to Reyes (2020), despite of the implementation of the values program of NSTP, the call for evaluation based on the status, challenges and impact must be done also to create a favourable and responsive program for students.

Also, it was observed that there are a lot of students who don't give importance on their NSTP subject particularly in LTS and CWTS. As what some students says when they are ask about what they have learned in their NSTP class, some of the students states that they learned nothing about the subject because their professor or instructor did not teach the whole semester aside from asking them to plant a tree and sweep the yard. Aside from that according to some NSTP faculty, they don't have a standardized topics in teaching NSTP literacy training service and civic welfare training service.

In TSU, some topics particularly about first aid are not discuss and demonstrate properly because of the inability of THE resources such the equipment for teaching cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR).

Thus, the present study will be undertaken to determine the abovementioned gaps and to know the practices and challenges of NSTP trainers in Tertiary Education particularly in the province of Tarlac and the result of the study may serve as the basis for a proposed management plan.

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Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to know the Practices and Challenges of NSTP in Tertiary Education in Tarlac.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of NSTP non-military trainers along areas of?
 - 1.1 age,
 - 1.2 gender,
 - 1.3 Marital status,
 - 1.4 Religion,
 - 1.5 Designation/Affiliation,
 - 1.6 Educational qualification,
 - 1.7 Trainings and seminars attended relative to NSTP, and
 - 1.8 Years of Teaching Experiences in NSTP?
2. What are the practices in NSTP be described by the participants in terms of;
 - 2.1 Orientation of teachers,
 - 2.2 Preparation of syllabus,
 - 2.3 methods and strategy,
 - 2.4 assessment tools, and
 - 2.5 school's best practices?
3. What are the challenges encountered by the participants in Teaching NSTP?
4. What training management plan can be proposed based on the findings of the study?
5. What is the implication of the study to educational management?

Significance of the Study

The study was conducted to know the practices and challenges of NSTP in Tertiary Education particularly in the Province of Tarlac will give the following significance:

To SUCs and PHEI Administrators. The trainers' profile, the problems encountered, and the practices of NSTP teachers may serve as the basis for enhancing the training of the School/University in NSTP subjects.

To the Teachers. The result of this study may help them enhance their teaching strategies and know which assessment tools should be used in conducting NSTP classes.

To the Students. The result of this study may enable them to improve and enhance their training performance with their chosen component and help them to have a direct training experience.

To the Parents. The result of this study would assure parents that their children received a quality education that help them to strengthen their civic and community responsibilities.

To the Future Researcher. The result of the study can serve as a basis for further research on evaluating the training management systems of schools and can serve as reference data in conducting new research.

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Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study aims to assess the challenges and practices of NSTP particularly the Literacy training service and Civic welfare training service component of Tertiary education in the Province of Tarlac.

The study utilized a descriptive survey questionnaire to be validated by NSTP coordinators/leaders wherein 2 SUCs and 10 PHEI in Tarlac was the source of data.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

The literature and studies cited tackle the different concepts, understanding, ideas, generalizations or conclusions, and other developments related to the topic, which serve as the researcher's guide in developing the study.

Encouraging today's youth to train and work with people from diverse cultural groups, emphasizing partnerships between the projects and communities, and understanding their role in enacting change in the community as globalization expands was very challenging. Teachers need to have effective training management such as strategies in teaching, effective assessment tools, and excellent syllabi wherein students learn through direct experience or performance tasks for them to learn efficiently and effectively about their civic responsibility.

Performance tasks are learning activities or assessments where students can demonstrate their ability knowledge and understanding of the subject. It can help students to attain lifelong knowledge and skills (McTighe, 2015). These life-long skills may be used for the self-improvement of the students towards the demonstration of their competencies and civic responsibility.

Thus, hiring a well-competent instructor or teacher is very important. As what the DepEd says, "Teachers should be hired based on merit, fitness, and competence." Therefore, knowing the profile of the teachers or instructor such as their degree, seminars and training before entering teaching path will help schools and universities to have a well competent and quality education to offer.

Qualified, effective, and diverse teachers and leaders in a workforce are a must-have to make a quality education and training towards the students because the best way to invest in students is to invest in teachers first (American Institute for Research). Thus, offering training and seminars for teachers in relation to their teaching load is very helpful to improve and develop the craft of each mentor in school. Training and seminars will help teachers to create an effective learning environment, improve teaching-learning situations, keep updated on modern instructional devices and inspire them to become better teachers in the modern world. (Felipe, Ruvirosa, 2013). Also, according to Alton-Lee the teachers should align their professional experiences with their teaching practices and pedagogies to benefit their students.

Agreeing to Alton-Lee, one of the major roles of the teachers especially this new normal is to ensure that the content delivered has achieved the learning objective of the course, which can be considered a key challenge especially in teaching NSTP since community needs and demands may change time to time. So, the teachers should also

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undergo professional and personal development to benefit both the students and them as well; both are the learners.

In the study conducted by A.S. Francisco, (2020), in delivering quality instruction, teachers' demographic characteristics such as their academic degree, training and seminars have been one of the most important considerations for developing an educational system. It shows that professional demographic characteristics of a teacher can affect students' academic performance.

Thus, the researcher wants also to evaluate the profile of NSTP trainers specifically their academic degree, trainings and seminars attended because it shows in the study that every unit improvement in the professional demographic characteristics of a teacher such as trainings and seminars could generate a 1.528 increase in students' academic performance. They also found that students taught by teachers with higher qualifications performed better.

In the study conducted by K. Losabia and C. Gabriel (2015) about the impact of participation of Lyceum of the Philippines –Laguna in NSTP, it showed that majority of the students perceived that they have learned from NSTP service-learning with a mean of 4.06. Basically, students learn from their experiences in the community by becoming socially aware of the problems in the community. They also learn to improve their critical thinking skills, leadership skills even their personal spiritual growth among others.

In the study conducted by E. Victoria (2017) towards the CWTS contextualized practice of the HEI in Central Luzon by faculty and students' perception across CWTS areas such as syllabi, activities, and evaluation scheme when subjected to ANOVA indicate an f-value equivalent to 2.903, which is found lower than the critical value of 2.99, set at $\alpha=.05$ level of significance. It shows that faculty ratings were found higher than the students' ratings. Therefore, findings signify that a discrepancy on the perception towards the CWTS contextualized practice is evident and may imply that the faculty/facilitators are articulating the IRR for CWTS course, but not fully translating it to the students through instruction.

In addition to that, NSTP courses influenced the self-improvement of the students positively according to the study of M. L. Balmeo et al (2015) about The Effects of NSTP on the Lives of Saint Louis University Students, it shows that through attending NSTP classes, students learned more about leadership, developed their selves professionally, improved their academic performance, have chance to connect with other students and communities and improved their self-confidence. School of accountancy business management, engineering and architecture, natural science, nursing, and teacher education have their highest weighted means on the item on performing community service better. Their highest computed weighted means are 2.92, 3.08, 3.27, 3.36, and 3.19 respectively. While the highest computed weighted value on the item on the increased of understanding of leadership and community development signified by the computed weighted value of 3.01. Also, NSTP courses were able to influence the community involvement of the students since it enables them to identify what improvements are to be made to the situation of the target group and what results will be needed to generate specific impact, which is evidenced by their highest computed weighted mean of 3.00.

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These cited studies by K. Losabia and C. Gabriel (2015), M. L. Balmeo et al (2015) and E. Victoria (2017) has significance on the present study because the present study wants also to assess the challenges and practices of NSTP teachers particularly those teachers who teach LTS and CWTS among SUCs and PHEI in Tarlac Province.

In the study conducted by A. Zapata about the National Service Training Program of State Colleges and Universities: An Assessment, respondents of the six state universities perceived that the NSTP objectives were not accomplished effectively and that the fund allotment and school facilities were not adequate and the faculty on the other hand, had no necessary/related experience with regard to training to handle for the NSTP subject based on their educational qualification.

She also recommended that management should support the program in works and in deeds especially in allotting adequate funds to meet goals; and sufficient budget significantly affects the increase in the student's performance and productivity of the facilitators. There should be enough lecture rooms, facilities rooms conducive to learning and sufficient books and references that will enhance and facilitate learning and awareness of the students about the effectiveness, efficiency, responsiveness, appropriateness equity and adequacy of the program.

Conceptual Framework

Civic consciousness influences the progress of the state and society. In the absence of civic consciousness, human beings will become selfish, and all their activities will be for their achievements. To ensure the welfare of all and the reconstruction of society, civic consciousness must be developed. Thus, the creation of NSTP concretely addresses the skills and attitudes that are needed in preparing the students to make significant contributions to themselves and their communities as well. (CHED, 2002).

The National Service Training Program (NSTP) of the Philippines is a form of service learning that is defined as the integration of community services into instruction to strengthen the civic and community responsibilities of the students. LTS and CWTS a program components of NSTP designed to train students to become responsible, particularly in their community. It is composed of different topics aligned with community involvement such as disaster preparedness, environmental protection, good citizenship values, volunteering, and conducting community service such as tutoring and teaching.

Moreover, Reyes (2009) discovered that implementers of non-military program components perceived certain problems along community/extension, information management programs, and monitoring and evaluation programs considered serious. Thus, an evaluation based on the status, challenges, and impact of the NSTP must be done.

This study focused on the challenges and practices of NSTP in Tertiary education in Tarlac.

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The primary objective of the study is to evaluate the practices and challenges of the National Service Training Program- Literacy Training Service and Civic Welfare Training Service in Tertiary education in Tarlac province based on their profile in terms of school, academic degree, training, seminars, and years of teaching experiences. The profile of the respondents was analyzed to have a better understanding of the relevance of their profile to NSTP.

The practices of NSTP trainers also be described in terms of the orientation of teachers, preparation of syllabus, methods, and strategies, and use of assessment tools. Schools' best practices were also identified based on the description of the respondents on their practices.

The challenges encountered in teaching NSTP, particularly LTS, and CWTS were also discussed. This enables the institution to know how to address the challenges encountered. The implications of the findings of the study will be formulated.

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CHAPTER 2

METHODS OF STUDY AND SOURCES OF DATA

This chapter discusses the research method used in this study. It covers the discussion of the research design, sources of data, the respondents, the data gathering procedures, and the statistical measures.

Quantitative Design and Methodology

The descriptive research design was used in this study. Calderon (2006) defined descriptive research as a purposive process of describing, analyzing, classifying, and tabulating data about prevailing conditions. This design was employed to describe the profile of the respondents such as their age, gender, religion, marital status, designation, training and seminars, and years of teaching experience in NSTP. Likewise, the same descriptive design was used to describe challenges encountered in NSTP.

Research Locale

Tarlac province is a landlocked province in the Philippines located in the Central Luzon region. Its capital is the city of Tarlac. It is bounded in the north by the province of Pangasinan, Nueva Ecija on the east, Zambales on the west and Pampanga in the south. The province comprises three congressional districts and is subdivided into 17 municipalities and one city, Tarlac City, which is the provincial capital. The province is situated in the heartland of Luzon, in what is known as the Central Plain also spanning the neighboring provinces of Pampanga, Pangasinan, Nueva Ecija and Bulacan. Tarlac covers a total land area of 3,053.45 km² (305,345 ha). It has a total of 32 schools for college, 2 universities and 30 private institutions located in different municipalities. Out of 32 schools, 2 universities and 10 PHEI who offer LTS and/or CWTS will be the source of data.

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Figure 2: Tarlac Province Map (Source: Google)

Research Participants

The respondents on this study were 57 faculties who teach NSTP in different SUCs and PHEI in Tarlac who offers CWTS and LTS NSTP component.

The study was conducted during the First semester of the Academic Year 2023 – 2024.

Sampling Design

The table provided shows the sample size of the participants. The selection of research participants was conducted through full enumeration ensuring that the 57 faculty members from the schools were included in the study.

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Table 1: List of the Participants

School	No. of Respondent
AMA College Tarlac	1
CIT Colleges Paniqui	2
Dominican College of Tarlac	3
Gerona Junior College	1
Interworld College Foundation Inc	2
Osias Colleges	2
Philippine Women's University - CDCEC – Tarlac	3
Saint Paul Colleges Foundation – Paniqui	1
Saint Rose College Educational Foundation	1
STI College – Tarlac	3
Tarlac Agricultural University	13
Tarlac State University	25
TOTAL	57

Research Instrument and Data Collection

In the first phase, the researcher asks permission from the heads or authorities in schools to conduct a study. A letter of consent will be given to allow a researcher to conduct a study.

A researcher's descriptive questionnaire used in this study was validated by the 3 experts from Don Honorio Ventura State University (2) and Pampanga State University (1) who are in the field of teaching NSTP- director and component coordinators. The questionnaire content was composed of four (4) parts: The first part of the questionnaire is about the profile of the respondents followed by the description of the NSTP practices; challenges encountered and the recommended training plan.

Also, the researcher utilized structured interviews to elicit specific answers from respondents.

Data analysis

To interpret the data effectively, the researcher employed the following statistical treatment:

Frequency counts and Percentages. To count the number of times that each variables occurs, frequency counts and percentage will use. This formula was used to determine the counts of the profile and the challenges of NSTP trainers.

$$P=f \times 100\% / N$$

Where: p=percentage
f- Frequency
N-number of cases

Mean. To describe the practices in NSTP, the mean was determined by the following formula:

$$\bar{x} = f \times N$$

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Where, \bar{x} -mean
 f-frequency
 x-weight of the score
 N-number of cases

To interpret practices of NSTP trainers, the scale below was used:

Table 2

Scoring interpretation on the practices of NSTP trainers' questionnaire

Index	Mean Score	Verbal Description
5	4.50 - 5.00	Always
4	3.50 - 4.49	Sometimes
3	2.50 - 3.49	Neutral
2	1.50 - 2.49	Often
1	1.00 - 1.49	Never

Index	Mean Score	Verbal Description
5	4.50 - 5.00	Very Important
4	3.50 - 4.49	Important
3	2.50 - 3.49	Neutral
2	1.50 - 2.49	Less Important
1	1.00 - 1.49	Not Important

Ethical Consideration

The researcher prepared a letter seeking approval and permission from different universities and colleges in Tarlac. Also, the researcher informed the respondents about the purpose of the study and the significance of the findings. Additionally, the researcher informed the respondents that all the information gathered would be only used for the study and ensured the confidentiality and secrecy of the gathered data.

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CHAPTER 3

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

The result and analysis of the quantitative data about the practices and challenges of NSTP of tertiary education in Tarlac based on the results of the study were reviewed in this chapter.

1. Profile of National Service Training Program- Civic Welfare Training Service and Literacy Training Service trainers

Evaluating respondent profiles provides valuable insights into data analysis, assessment standards, and the stability of relationships, making it an important aspect of research and monitoring processes. It also helps the researcher to understand and check the stability of the functional relationship between a response variable and explanatory variables over time.

The figures below show the profile of NSTP Literacy Training Service and Civic Welfare training in terms of their age, sex, marital status, religion, designation, educational qualification, training and seminars, and years of teaching experience.

Profile of National Service Training Program- Civic Welfare Training Service and Literacy Training Service trainers in terms of;

1.1 Age

Figure 3: Profile of the respondents in terms of Age

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The data revealed that 51% of the NSTP trainers in Tarlac province belonged to 21-29, 14% for 30-35, 10% for 36-40, 9% for 41-45 and 50 years old above, and 7% for 46-50 years old. Since NSTP is a combination of academic and physical activities such as conducting community service, first aid training, and other field activities. Thus, 51 % of faculty members teaching NSTP were 21-29 years old because they were capable of teaching physical activities.

1.2 Sex

Figure 4: Profile of the respondents in terms of Sex

It can be seen in Figure 2 that 58% of the faculty members of NSTP were female and 42% were male. This means that the majority of the faculty teaching NSTP CWST and LTS were female. This implies that most of the tertiary education in Tarlac province prefer to have female faculty.

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1.3 Marital Status

Figure 5: Profile of the respondents in terms of Marital Status

The figure shows that 49% of the respondents were married, 46% were singles, 3% were widowed and 2% were separated

1.4 Religion

Figure 6: Profile of the respondents in terms of Religion

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It can be seen from the data above that 74% of the respondents belong to Roman Catholic, 12% were born again, 5% were Iglesia ni Cristo, 3% were Methodist, 2% were Jehovah's Witness and some of the respondents considered their selves as a Christian also. Since NSTP is composed of topics or lessons about good citizenship values, particularly about Maka-Diyos therefore religions of the respondents have a huge impact on how they delivered that lesson.

1.5 Designation

Figure 7: Profile of the respondents in terms of Designation

It can be seen from the data above that 70% of the respondents have a designation as Instructor, 12% were attached faculty from different school offices, 7% were NSTP coordinators the other 7% were school nurses and 4% were NSTP directors. Based on the conducted structured interviews, most of which had no permanent item which implied that the NSTP office does not prioritize giving permanent item for faculty. One of the reasons was almost half of the 70% had only a bachelor's degree. Also, the data showed that there was a school nurse teaching NSTP since one of the topics covered by the syllabus of that school was about first aid and basic life support.

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1.4 Highest Educational Attainment

Figure 8: Profile of the respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

It can be seen in the figure above that 58% of the respondents have a bachelor's degree, 23% have a master's degree, 10% have a professional education degree and 9% have a doctorate. The data implies that the hiring of NSTP faculty in Tarlac province required a bachelor's degree only as an educational qualification. This means, that attending trainings or seminars has a huge impact on the professional growth of the faculty members aside from convincing them to take master's degree.

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1.5 Years of teaching experience

Figure 9: Profile of the respondents in terms of years of teaching experience in NSTP

Figure above shows that 60% of the respondents have 1-3 years of experience in teaching NSTP, 23% have 4-6 years of experience, 7% have 7-10 years and 5% have 10-15 years of teaching experience and the other 5% have more than 15 years in teaching NSTP. One of the reasons why 60% of the respondents have 1-3 years of teaching experience in NSTP was because they belong to the 51% whose age ranges from 21-29 years old and who have a bachelor's degree.

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1.6 Training and seminars attended related to NSTP

Table 2

Training and Seminars attended related to NSTP

Training and Seminars attended related to NSTP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International NSTP Implementers Conference 	20	35.08%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solid Waste Management Training and Seminar 	1	1.75%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pollution Control 	1	1.75%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbon Segregation 	1	1.75%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NSTP Unlad 2022 	5	8.77%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic First Aid and Basic life Support 	30	52.63%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contextualization of NSTP program offered by TAU 	1	1.75%
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic Occupational Safety and Health for Safety Officer I 	1	1.75%

When it comes to attended training and seminars, it can be seen on the table that 52.63% of NSTP trainers particularly from TSU have training in first aid and basic life support. Since first aid and basic life support were some of the required training in teaching NSTP LTS and CWTS at Tarlac State University thus, faculty members attended training and seminars about that topic. 35.08% or 20 out of 57 respondents attended the international NSTP implementers' conference. One faculty member or 1.75% of the respondents has a seminar and/or training related to solid waste management, pollution control, contextualization of the NSTP program and basic occupational safety and health for safety officers since those topics were related to the topics that they want to focus in teaching LTS and CWTS which is about disaster preparedness and awareness.

2. Practices of National Service Training Program- Literacy Training Service and Civic Welfare Training Service in Private Higher Educational Institution.

2.1 Orientation of Teachers

Conducting orientations was very important to provide opportunities to enhance pedagogical knowledge and introduce effective instructional strategies in teaching. It also helps to develop and enhance the teaching and learning process.

Table 4 and Table 5 present the practices of tertiary education in Tarlac in terms of the orientation of faculty members.

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Table 3

Practices of the Participants in Private Higher Educational Institution as to orientation of teachers

	Mean	Verbal Description
Faculties and trainers undergo orientation particularly about RA 9163(NSTP Law) before teaching NSTP.	3.06	Neutral
Conducting an orientation for LTS and CWTS syllabus before teaching NSTP.	4.36	Sometimes
Faculties have planning, coaching, and mentoring before the start of the semester.	4.06	Sometimes

It can be seen in Table 3 revealed by NSTP faculty in private institutions, "Faculty member undergo orientation, particularly about NSTP law (RA 91630 and its IRR (Implementing Rules and regulations before teaching NSTP)" obtained a mean score of 3.06 which has a verbal description of neutral. Since some institutions have only one (1) faculty teaching NSTP. Conducts orientation for LTS (Literacy Training Service) and CWTS (Civic Welfare Training Service) syllabus before teaching NSTP obtained a mean score of 4.36 with a verbal description of sometimes. Faculty members who have planning, coaching, and mentoring before and during the start of the semester got a mean score of 4.06 which has a verbal description of Sometimes. This implies that 50% of the respondents don't have an orientation and don't know anything about RA 9163(NSTP Act) and its implementing rules and regulations before teaching NSTP. According to one respondent from a private tertiary institution, they just only asked to teach NSTP even though they were not aligned to teach that course subject. Also, it shows that planning, coaching, and mentoring happen sometimes. One of the reasons was that there's only one (1) faculty teaching NSTP. Thus, respondents from two institutions suggest that all NSTP trainers in Tarlac province should have even though once or twice training seminars every semester, especially about RA 9163, or NSTP Act of 2001, or any related topics about NSTP.

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Table 4

Practices of the Participants in State Universities as to orientation of teachers

	Mean	Verbal Description
Faculties and trainers undergo orientation particularly about RA 9163(NSTP Law) before teaching NSTP.	4.29	Sometimes
Conducting an orientation for LTS and CWTS syllabus before teaching NSTP.	4.64	Always
Faculties have planning, coaching, and mentoring before the start of the semester.	4.13	Sometimes

Table 4 revealed that the orientation of teachers particularly about RA 9163(NSTP Law) before teaching NSTP got a mean score of 4.29 for a verbal description of "Sometimes" which according to the respondents from one university, they just only did the orientation about RA 9163 if there's a newly hired faculty for NSTP. While "Conducting an orientation for LTS and CWTS syllabus before teaching NSTP" got a verbal description of "always" which has a mean score of 4.64. This will serve also as their refresher course according to the respondent from one university.

Furthermore, planning, coaching, and mentoring before the start of the semester happens only sometimes. According to the respondents, it should happen before, during, and after the semesters for the professional development of the faculty members.

2.2 Preparation of Syllabus

Syllabus serves as a learning tool for students. It is a document that expresses to the students the intentions of the instructor regarding course content, learning goals, assessment approach, and expectations. It outlines what is expected to transpire during the course and what should be learned.

In preparation NSTP syllabus it is very important to highlight topics or lessons to develop civic consciousness and defense preparedness of the students.

Table 5 presents the practices of tertiary education in Tarlac in terms of the preparation of syllabi.

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Table 5

2.2.1 Preparation of Syllabus for Civic Welfare Training Service

AREAS OF CONCERN	MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Provides basic information about the subject (title, subject number, credit hours)	4.81	Very Important
Grading criteria	4.72	Very Important
Inculcate the spirit of patriotism, nationalism, and good citizenship values to enhance the civic consciousness of the students	4.67	Very Important
Includes subject policies	4.63	Very Important
Includes calendar of assignments, activities and exams.	4.61	Very Important
Instill topics about good manners and right conduct	4.59	Very Important
Include topics about first aid and basic life support for them to have knowledge on how to save lives.	4.55	Very Important
Includes topics about volunteerism and its role in volunteering for the students to know the importance of volunteering.	4.50	Very Important
Includes topics regards to RA 10121 (Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction Management) such as earthquake drill, fire drill and other related topics about DRR for the students to be prepared when disaster/s arise.	4.46	Important
Includes topics about self-awareness and values development	4.42	Important
Includes topics about environmental protection and management to develop the environmental awareness of the students.	4.36	Important
Includes topics about community and community needs assessment.	4.36	Important
Includes topics about personality development	4.36	Important
Includes topics about leadership and sense of teamwork	4.30	Important
Includes topics about drug education to give students knowledge especially about the illegal drugs and the effects of it.	4.28	Important
Includes topics about health program such as blood donation and registry	3.90	Important

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Includes topics about entrepreneurship and livelihood	3.69	Important
Syllabus composed of 25 hours common module and 29 hours specific module.	3.17	Important

Table 6 founds out that providing basic information about the subject (title, subject number, credit hours), including criteria for grading, subject policies, calendar of assignments, activities, and exams and inserting topics about good citizenship values, patriotism, and nationalism enhance the civic consciousness of the students, good manners and right conduct, disaster preparedness and awareness, environmental protection, drug education, volunteerism, first aid training, are the very important topics that must include in preparing the syllabus for CWTS. While community needs assessment, personality development such as self-awareness and values development and leadership, health, and entrepreneurship are important topics also for CWTS. Philippine constitution especially human rights, mental health awareness, and the importance of our natural resources was also suggested to be included in the CWTS syllabus.

Table 6

2.2.2 Preparation of Syllabus for Literacy Training Service

AREAS OF CONCERN	MEAN	VERBAL DESCRIPTION
Includes subject policies	4.89	Very Important
Includes topics about self-awareness and values development	4.86	Very Important
Inculcate the spirit of patriotism, nationalism, and good citizenship values to enhance the civic consciousness of the students	4.80	Very Important
Includes calendar of assignments, activities and exams.	4.77	Very Important
Grading criteria	4.77	Very Important
Provides basic information about the subject (title, subject number, credit hours)	4.73	Very Important
Instil topics about good manners and right conduct	4.66	Very Important
Includes topics regards to RA 10121 (Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction Management) such as earthquake drill, fire drill and other related topics about	4.66	Very Important

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DRR for the students to be prepared when disaster/s arise.		
Includes topics about Literacy and Numeracy	4.66	Very Important
Syllabus composed of 25 hours common module and 29 hours specific module.	4.66	Very Important
Includes topics about community and community needs assessment.	4.66	Very Important
Includes subject policies	4.64	Very Important
Includes calendar of assignments, activities, and exams.	4.57	Very Important
Include topics about first aid and basic life support for them to have knowledge on how to save lives.	4.53	Very Important
Includes topics about environmental protection and management to develop the environmental awareness of the students.	4.53	Very Important
Includes topics about leadership and sense of teamwork	4.46	Important
Includes topics about personality development	4.46	Important
Includes topics about volunteerism and its role in volunteering for the students to know the importance of volunteering.	4.46	Important
Includes topics about drug education to give students knowledge especially about the illegal drugs and the effects of it.	4.40	Important
Includes topics about entrepreneurship and livelihood	3.86	Important

In Table 7, it can be seen that providing basic information about the subject (title, subject number, credit hours), including subject policies, grading criteria, calendar of assignments, activities, and exams are very important aspects that must be included in preparing syllabus for Literacy Training Service. It was also found that most of the variables included in the questionnaires are very important in teaching LTS, particularly topics about self-awareness and values development which has a mean score of 4.86. According to the respondents, the following topics were very important in developing and enhancing the civic awareness and consciousness of the students. Including topics about entrepreneurship and livelihood was also important but when compared to the following variables, topics about entrepreneurship and livelihood got the lowest mean score of 3.86.

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It was also suggested that mental health awareness, psychological first aid, sex education, and special education and people with special needs must be included in the LTS syllabus.

2.3 Methods and Strategies

Teaching methods and strategies plays an important role in classroom instruction. Having methods and strategies in teaching facilitate a more active learning environment and help teacher to assess students understanding.

Table 8 and table 9 presents the practices of the tertiary education in Tarlac in terms of Methods and Strategies.

Table 7

2.3.1 Training on methods or Strategies in Teaching Civic Welfare Training Service

VARIABLES	N	%	RANK
Used Lecture and showing in teaching CWTS	51	98.07%	1
Conducting an interactive lectures in teaching CWTS	50	96.15%	2
Used skills-based teaching and learning.	46	88.46%	3
Use Seminar/webinar in teaching NSTP lessons.	45	86.53%	4
Used Discussion-based in teaching CWTS	42	80.76%	5
Used Collaborative Learning in teaching CWTS	42	80.76%	6
Used Scenario-based in teaching CWTS	37	71.15%	7
Used Case-based in teaching CWTS	33	63.46%	8
Used Problem-based in teaching CWTS	30	57.69%	9
Used Inquiry-based in teaching CWTS	27	51.92%	10

Table 7 shows that 51 out of 52 or 98.07% of the faculties prepared to use lectures and showing in teaching CWTS followed by using skills-based (88.46%). Conducting seminars about CWTS topics was also used (86.53%), the discussion-based and collaborative base which has a mean score of 80.76%. Respondents from one institution in

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Paniqui Tarlac also agreed that discussion and collaborative learning were very important in teaching. Meanwhile, 27 out of 52 or 51.92% of the respondents also prepared to use inquiry guided which has a lower average mean score among the above data in table 8.

Table 8

2.3.2 Training on methods or Strategies in Teaching Literacy Training Service

VARIABLES	N	%	RANK
Used Discussion-based in teaching LTS.	15	100	1
Used Collaborative Learning in teaching LTS.	15	100	1
Used skills-based teaching and learning.	15	100	1
Use Seminar/webinar in teaching LTS lessons.	14	93.33	2
Conducting an Interactive lectures in teaching LTS	12	80	3
Used Lecture and showing in teaching LTS	10	66.66	4
Used Problem-based in teaching LTS	10	66.66	5
Used Inquiry-based in teaching LTS	9	60	6
Used Scenario-based in teaching LTS	7	46.66	7
Used Case-based in teaching LTS	7	46.66	8

Table 8 shows that discussion-based, collaborative learning, and skills-based are prepared to be used in teaching LTS which has an average score of 100%. It was also found that conducting or using seminars or webinars in teaching LTS lessons was important which according to the 3 respondents, conducting seminars in teaching LTS can help, inform and train students about topics such as drug education, environmental issues, and mental health awareness. Meanwhile, 7 out of 15, or 46.66% of the respondents also prepared to use scenario and case-based in teaching LTS.

This implies that teaching literacy training service and civic welfare training services is a combination of theoretical discussions and skills not just only about planting trees and sweeping the yards.

2.4 Assessment tool

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Assessment are one of the important parts of the teaching and learning process. It determines what students have learned and helps teachers also to improve the teaching-learning process.

Tables 10 and 11 present the practices of tertiary education in Tarlac in terms of assessment tools.

Table 9

2.4.1 Assessment tools used in teaching Civic Welfare Training Service.

VARIABLES	N	%	RANK
Used demonstration in assessing the performance of the students	47	90.38 %	1
Used performance task to assess the students such as role playing, video making, etc.	46	88.46 %	2
Ask students to do a minor/major project such as outreach program, community engagement, case study, Disaster Risk Reduction Skills, etc.	42	80.76 %	3
Used written works or activities	42	80.76 %	4
Allow students to conduct seminars or workshops as part of assessing their knowledge in a certain topic in their community.	39	75 %	5
Allow students to do a self-reflection as part of an assessment tool.	39	75 %	6

It was found in Table 9 that the most used assessment tool in assessing the performance of the CWTS students was a demonstration which garnered a 47 out of 52 or 90.38% according to the three (3) respondents, demonstration of good citizenship values and other lessons in NSTP particularly CWTS such as first aid can be assessed through demonstration or conducting a performance task (88.46%). Asking students to do a minor/major project such as an outreach program, community engagement, and case study about disaster risk reduction skills was also used as part of an assessment tool in teaching NSTP-CWTS which has a rate of 80.76%. Written works and activities were also part of assessment tools in teaching CWTS which has a mean score of 80.76. This also shows that

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allowing students to conduct seminars and do self-reflection was not mostly used in assessing the performance of the students which has a least mean score of 75%.

Table 10

2.4.2 Assessment tools used in teaching Literacy Training Service.

VARIABLES	N	%	RANK
Used written works or activities	13	86.66	1
Used performance task to assess the students such as role playing, video making, etc.	13	86.66 %	1
Used demonstration in assessing the performance of the students	10	66.66 %	2
Allow students to conduct seminars or workshops as part of assessing their knowledge in a certain topic in their community.	10	66.66 %	3
Allow students to do a self-reflection as part of an assessment tool.	9	60.6%	4
Ask students to do a minor/major project such as outreach program, community engagement, case study, Disaster Risk Reduction Skills, etc.	8	53.33 %	5

In teaching LTS, table 10 shows that written works and activities and having a performance task were prepared tools for assessing the performance of the students. It shows that 86.66% of the respondents who teach NSTP used written works and performance tasks in assessing students' performance followed by demonstrations and allowing them to conduct seminars and webinars (66.66%). Self-reflection and asking students to do a minor or major project got a lower mean score of 60.6% and 53.33%. The data gathered implied that doing written activities and performance tasks such as about the importance of literacy and numeracy serve as evidence of learning in teaching literacy training services.

2.5 School's best Practices

Indeed PH describes best practices as a set of methods and techniques that produce optimal results, increase efficiency, and develop structured processes. A best practice is the most efficient and effective course of action in a particular situation.

Based on the result of the study, the school's best practices were as follows; Faculty members undergo orientation, particularly about RA 9163 or the NSTP act of 2001

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orientation about NSTP- LTS and CWTS syllabus and have coaching and mentoring before, during, and after the semester.

The preparation of the syllabus; provides basic information about the subject, including subject policies, including topics about good citizenship values and values development such as good manners and right conduct, volunteerism, disaster awareness and preparedness, and basic first aid.

The use of interactive lectures, showing, and skills-based teaching and learning are considered best practices when it comes to methods and strategies in teaching CWTS. While discussion-based, collaborative learning, and skills-based teaching and learning for LTS.

It was also perceived by the respondents that using demonstration, performance tasks, and asking students to do a minor/ major project such as an outreach program, community engagement, and case study could be a best practice or tool for assessing CWTS students. While written works or activities are used for performance tasks and demonstrations for LTS.

Also, some respondents from tertiary education in Tarlac considered the following as their best practices also; 1. Conducting outreach programs from different communities and school-based clean-up drives. 2. First Aid training for both teachers and students. 3. Water Survival and Rescue Training (WASAR). 4. Joining Gawad Kalasag as part of NSRC (National Service Reserve Corp) Community-Based Unit for TAU.

Another respondent also suggested having their best practices for the professional growth of the faculty members such as monthly training and workshops or seminars related to NSTP. Best practices for the environment, values development, and community engagement aside from the outreach program.

3. Challenges encountered in teaching National Service Training Program- Civic Welfare Training Service and Literacy Training Service

There are various challenges faced by the teacher from the students to the school environment. In this study, the lack of facilities, equipment, and supplies that may be used in teaching and the lack of provisions for training and seminars were top-billed in the results of this study.

Table 12 and Table 13 shows the challenges encountered by tertiary education in Tarlac Province.

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Table 11

Results of the challenges encountered in teaching NSTP- CWTS and LTS for Private Higher Educational Institution.

VARIABLES	N	%
1. Lack of provisions for trainings and seminars	18	94.73%
2. Attitudes and behaviour of the students	17	89.47%
3. Lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds	16	84.21%
4. Lack of Barangay Leaders Support in conducting community program/service.	14	73.68%
5. Lack of facilities, equipment and supplies that may use in teaching.	14	73.68%
6. No clear direction for the organization and mobilization of NSTP graduates	12	63.15%
7. Lack of Feedback Mechanism (Monitoring and Evaluation)	9	47.36%
8. lack of administrative support	9	47.36 %
9. Large number of students	6	31.57 %
10. Lack of Resources such as textbooks, modules and reference books	4	21 %

Table 11 revealed that the lack of provisions for training and seminars was perceived as the highest challenge faced by the NSTP CWTS and LT's private tertiary education in Tarlac which got a score of 94.73%. Since most of the faculty members based on the result of the study don't undergo training and seminars related to NSTP thus lack of training and seminars was perceived as the number one challenge encountered by the private institution in Tarlac province. Attitudes and behaviors of the students were perceived also as a top challenge encountered by the respondents (89.47%), lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds (84.21%) especially for CWTS and LTS component according to the respondents from one institution in Paniqui Tarlac. Three (3) respondents from PHEI in Tarlac also said that their school was not prioritizing NSTP when it comes to the allocation of budget they also experienced a lack of administrative support which according to the findings, lack of administrative support was one of the problems and challenges also experience by the 47.36% of the respondents and the lack of feedback mechanisms such as monitoring and evaluation for teachers, students and other related activities in NSTP. Respondents from one institution also added that their school must also provide at least 1 or 2 instructors who teach NSTP, particularly CWTS since he is only the one who teaches NSTP in their school. Furthermore, the lack of barangay leaders' support in conducting community outreach programs and the Lack of facilities, equipment, and

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supplies that may be used in teaching were also found out as the problems and challenges encountered which has a respondent of 73.68%. One respondent also said that whenever they conduct community service, some barangay leaders don't give support for the event even their presence. 63.15% for the no clear direction for the organization and mobilization of NSTP graduates, 31.57 % for a large number of students, and 21 % for the lack of Resources such as textbooks, modules, and reference books.

Table 12

Results of the challenges encountered in teaching NSTP CWTS and LTS for Universities.

VARIABLES	N	%
1. Lack of facilities, equipment and supplies that may use in teaching.	26	68.42%
2. Large number of students	23	60.52%
3. No clean direction for the organization and mobilization of graduates	22	57.89%
4. Lack of provisions for trainings and seminars	20	52.63%
5. Lack of Resources such as textbooks, modules and reference books	20	52.63%
6. Lack of Feedback Mechanism (Monitoring and Evaluation)	20	52.63%
7. Lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds	19	50%
8. Attitudes and behavior of the students	13	34.21%
9. lack of administrative support	12	31.57%
10. Lack of Barangay Leaders Support in conducting community program/service.	11	28.94%

It can be seen in Table 12 that the number one challenge faced by the NSTP trainers from two universities in Tarlac province was the lack of facilities, equipment, and supplies that may be used in teaching (68.42%) which according to the five respondents from Tarlac State University, one of the reasons was because of the large number of students (60.52%) which was the second highest problems and challenges encountered by NSTP trainers followed by the no clear direction for the organization and mobilization of NSTP graduates, lack of provisions for training and seminars and lack of resources such as textbooks, modules and reference books, lack of Feedback Mechanism (Monitoring and Evaluation) (52.63%), lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds (50%), attitudes and behavior of the students (34.21%), lack of administrative support (31.57%), lack of barangay leaders support in conducting community program/service (28.94%), too many topics (21.05%).

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Also, the always changing topics and syllabus, not sticking to the said plan, and lack of proper planning according to the respondents from one university.

It was observed from the result that two (2) universities considered lack of facilities and equipment as the top challenges encountered by the respondents. Since there are a lot of students enrolled in that school/s, thus lacking school facilities may be experienced. While for private colleges, it was the lack of training and seminars which according to the respondent from private tertiary education, their school was not prioritizing NSTP course.

Also, respondents from one private tertiary education added the lack of trained NSTP teachers. Always changing topics and syllabus, not sticking to the said plan, and imbalanced training for NSTP since most of the training was for ROTC, and lack of proper planning according to the respondents from one university. Respondents from private institutions also stated that CHED must provide a standard program of instructions and lessons for LTS and CWTS.

4. Proposed Training Management Plan

The proposed training management plan presented in this study was derived based on the findings of the study on the challenges encountered by the Tertiary education in Tarlac Province.

Challenges:

- Lack of provisions for trainings and seminars

Goals/ Objectives:

1. Equip faculty members' skills and knowledge related to NSTP particularly CWTS and LTS.

Strategies:

1. Coordinate with AFP, PNP, DND, or any accredited non-government organization (NGO) to formulate or administered trainings or seminars related to NSTP lessons.
2. Attend conference, training, or workshop related to NSTP conducted by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and technical education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), in consultation with the Department of National Defense (DND), Philippine Association of State Universities and Colleges (PASUC), Coordinating Council of Private Educational Associations of the Philippines (COCOPEA).

Time Frame:

Quarterly, once a month or before the starts of the semester

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Persons Involved:

1. Faculty
2. NSTP Director or coordinator
3. Local Government Unit
4. Department of National Defense
5. Philippine Association of State Universities and Colleges (PASUC)
6. Coordinating Council of Private Educational Associations of the Philippines (COCOPEA).
7. PDRRM, PNP, AFP, NGOs

Budget: POE or NSTP trust funds

Challenges:

- Lack of facilities, equipment and supplies that may be used in teaching.

Goals/Objectives:

1. Seek financial assistance or request letter from the government offices particularly from the provincial government office for the construction of facilities, or for the needed supplies and equipment particularly in teaching Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Training.

Strategies:

1. Coordinate with the provincial government office or LGU to follow up the request for supplies and equipment

Time Frame:

Before the starts of the semester

Persons Involved:

1. NSTP Director/ Coordinators
2. Faculties
3. School head/admin
4. Budget office
5. LGU

Budget: May vary depends on the request

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Chief Executive Editor: Blesseddy M. Cervantes, EdD.

Managing Editor: Rolando D. Cervantes, DHum

International Editor: Ji Young Lee, EdD.

Challenges:

- Large number of students

Goals/Objectives:

1. To have a teacher- student ratio (1:50/60)

Strategies:

1. Hire enough faculty who are trained and knowledgeable in teaching NSTP subject and have a maximum number of students as benchmark.

Time Frame:

Before the start of the semester

Persons Involved:

1. NSTP Director/ Coordinator
2. Faculty
3. Human Resource Office

Budget: POE

Challenges:

- No clear direction for the organization and mobilization of graduates

Goals/Objectives:

1. Standardized deployment of NSCR (National Service Reserve Corps) graduate.

Strategies:

1. Coordinate with the Commission on higher education or Department of National Defense to have a standardized instruction for national service reserve corps (NSRC) graduates.
2. MOA (Memorandum of Agreement) between SBNU (School Based NSRC Unit) and the LGU or community.
3. Clustering of students per municipality.

Time Frame: Every end of the academic year

Persons Involved:

1. CHED
 2. DND
 3. Faculty
-

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4. NSTP director/ coordinator
5. NSTP Implementers
6. Students
7. LGU
8. Community

Budget: POE or NSTP Trust funds

Challenges:

- Lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds

Goals/Objectives:

- To have a proper distribution of allocated funds for NSTP.

Strategies:

1. NSTP Director/ coordinator should provide a proposal regarding NSTP activities and program of expenditure for its program components.

Time Frame:

Every start of the semester

Persons Involved:

1. NSTP Director/Coordinators
2. Budget office
3. School board
4. Stakeholders

Budget: POE or NSTP Trust fund

Challenges:

- Attitudes and behaviour of the students

Goals/Objectives:

1. Ensure the full implementation of CHED Memo Order No.09-s.2013 section 22 (Student discipline)

Strategies:

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1. Universities and colleges shall provide a well competent and trained discipline committee for the implementations of rules and regulations about students misconduct and behaviour
2. Include good manners and right conduct and values development in the course syllabus.

Time Frame:

All year round

Persons Involved:

1. School Administration
2. Human Resource Office
3. Guidance office/ counsellor
4. NSTP Director/ Coordinators
5. NSTP Faculty

Budget: POE

Challenges:

- Lack of Resources such as textbooks, modules and reference books

Goals/Objectives:

1. Conduct a seminar or training in preparation of modules or topics about NSTP particularly LTS and CWTS components

Strategies:

1. Coordinate with the commission on higher education or NSTP implementers for the creation of NSTP modules for universities and colleges following the citizenship training; drug education; disaster awareness, preparedness, and management; environmental protection; and other national security concerns for 25 hours and 29 hours for any related topics for LTS and CWTS.

Time Frame:

All year-round

Persons Involved:

1. CHED
2. NSTP Implementers
3. NSTP director/ coordinator
4. Faculty

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Budget: POE or NSTP Trust fund

Challenges:

- Lack of Feedback Mechanism (Monitoring and Evaluation) for faculty member.

Goals/Objectives: To have a monthly or quarterly monitoring and evaluation of NSTP faculty.

Strategies:

1. NSTP director or coordinator should provide or develop a monitoring or evaluation tool for the NSTP faculty.
2. Conduct a monthly coaching and mentoring.

Time Frame: Quarterly and monthly

Persons Involved:

1. NSTP Director
2. NSTP Coordinator
3. NSTP Faculty

Budget: POE

Challenges:

- Lack of administrative support

Goals/Objectives:

1. To promote administrative support especially in giving funds for NSTP activities.

Strategies:

Provide a Learning Development Plan with allocated budget for program component for the school administration or school head to know the needs of each NSTP program components

Time Frame: Every start of the semester

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Persons Involved:

1. NSTP director/ coordinator
2. Faculty
3. School head/admin

Budget: POE or NSTP Trust funds

Challenges: Lack of Barangay Leaders Support in conducting community program/service.

Goals/Objectives

- Establish a school and community partnership

Strategies:

NSTP office or coordinator should provide a Memorandum of Agreement between school and barangay/community.

Time Frame: All year round

Persons Involved:

1. NSTP Director/ coordinator
2. Faculty
3. Students
4. LGU

Budget: POE or NSTP Trust fund

5. Implication of the study to Educational Management

Educational Management was a field that was concerned with the operation of educational organizations. High-quality management provides a greater understanding and skills for achieving organizational goals. This study implies educational management. Wherein findings of the study encourage school administration or NSTP implementers should provide and support NSTP trainers especially when it comes to their activities to develop their professional growth such as conducting a seminar and workshop, or training related to NSTP since one of the problems and challenges encountered by NSTP trainers were lack of training and seminars. In this regard, the problem will be reduced.

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The result of the practices on assessment tools, methods, and strategies used in teaching NSTP- LTS and CWTS in this study will also help NSTP trainers to have good training management towards students.

School best practices may also serve as their reference to have and develop their own schools' best practices. Also, the suggested training management plan will serve as a point reference for the schools, universities, and private higher educational institutions in Tarlac province. Also, this will be helpful for them to know which topics must be included in teaching NSTP- Civic Welfare Training Service and Literacy Training Service.

CHAPTER 4

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of findings, conclusions and recommendations based on the results and analysis of gathered data.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were derived from the results of the study.

1. Profile of NSTP trainers

The NSTP trainers' profile were described based on their age, gender, religion, marital status, designation, educational qualification, trainings and seminars and the years of teaching experience.

1.1 Age

The result of the study shows that 50.88% of the age of teachers teaching NSTP in Tarlac province range to 21-29 years old. Therefore, the study concludes that there were a lot of Gen Z and millennial trainers who teach NSTP particularly Literacy Training Service and Civic Welfare Training Service which was relevant to the NSTP course since NSTP is a training course that has a lot of physical activities.

1.2 Gender

The study shows that 57.90% or 33 out of 57 NSTP trainers in Tarlac province were female and 42.10% were male.

1.3 Religion

It shows on the data conducted that 73.68% of the NSTP trainers were Roman Catholic and the rest belonged to other religions such as Iglesia ni Cristo and Born Again but they all considered their selves as Christian in general. The religion of the respondents identified in the study since NSTP subject also promotes the importance of Filipino Values such as being "Maka-Diyos.

1.4 Marital status

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On the conducted study 28% of the respondents were married 26% were single, 3.51% were widowed and 1.75% were separated.

1.5 Designation

It shows in the study that 70.18% (40) of the respondents were instructors and half of them did not have a permanent position. Also, 2 respondents were designated as NSTP directors who belong to State Universities, and 3 NSTP Coordinators.

1.6 Educational Qualifications

The study shows that 64.91% (37) of the trainers have finished a bachelor's degree 15.79% have a master's degree and 3.51% (2) had a doctorate. The data implied that hiring NSTP faculty requires only a bachelor's degree aside from being an NSTP Director.

1.7 Years of teaching experience/s

The data shows that 59.65% of the NSTP trainers have 1-3 years of teaching NSTP subjects because most of them are aged 21-29 years old and have a bachelor's degree.

1.8 Trainings and seminars related to NSTP.

It shows in the study that 52.63% of NSTP trainers particularly from TSU have training in first aid and basic life support. First aid and basic life support were some of the required training in teaching NSTP LTS and CWTS at Tarlac State University. 35.08% or 20 out of 57 respondents attended the international NSTP implementers' conference. One faculty member or 1.75% of the respondents has a seminar and/or training related to solid waste management, pollution control, contextualization of the NSTP program, and basic occupational safety and health for safety officers.

2. Practices in National Service Training Program

2.1 Orientation of Teachers

The findings of NSTP practices in terms of orientation of teachers about RA 9163 or NSTP act of 2001 obtained a mean score of 2.83 which has a verbal description of neutral which revealed that most of the NSTP trainers in Tarlac province don't undergo orientation particularly about the RA 9163 and it's IRR. Also, it was revealed that most of the schools and higher institutions in Tarlac have conducted planning, coaching, and mentoring. Orientation of syllabus for CWTS and LTS done sometimes which has a mean score of 4.14 and 4.42.

2.2 Preparation of Syllabus

When it comes on the preparation of syllabus, providing basic information about the subject, inserting the criteria for grading, including topics about citizenship values, RA 10121 (Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction Management, environmental protection, drug education, volunteerism, first aid, personal development such as self-awareness, leadership and values development are the

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very important topics that must be included in preparing the syllabus for both LTS and CWTS. In addition to that, teaching Literacy and Numeracy particularly functional literacy and numeracy in LTS are very important also.

2.3 Teaching Strategies

It shows on the study that in teaching CWTS, conducting lectures (98.07%), interactive lectures (96.15%) and skills-based teaching (88.46%) were the most used teaching methods and strategies followed by conducting a seminar or webinar (86.53). While in LTS, trainers prepare to use discussion, collaborative and skills-based which has a total score of 100%.

2.4 Assessment tools

The results of the study show that demonstrations and performance tasks are the assessment tools prepared to use by the CWTS trainers which have a total score of 90.38 % and 88.46%. While assessing LTS students, 86.66% of the LTS trainers prepare to use written assessments and performance tasks followed by the demonstration which has a mean score of 66.66 %.

2.5 School's best practices

The conducted data shows that conducting lectures and interactive lectures were the teaching methods used by the CWTS faculty members while using discussion, collaboration, and skills-based for LTS faculty. Also using assessment tools in teaching NSTP such as demonstrations and performance tasks was considered as best practice in assessing students learning.

Also, respondents added that conducting outreach or community programs, clean-up drives, and disaster preparedness such as first aid and basic life support training was considered also as their school's best practices.

3. Challenges encountered in Teaching National Service Training Program

The top five challenges encountered by the NTSP trainers in private higher educational institutions in Tarlac were 1. Lack of provisions for training and seminars, 2. Attitudes and behavior of the students, 3. Lack of proper allocation of NSTP funds, 4. Lack of Barangay Leaders' Support in conducting community programs/services and 5. Lack of facilities, equipment, and supplies that may be used in teaching. While in two (2) universities was 1. Lack of facilities, equipment, and supplies that may be used in teaching, 2. A large number of students, 3. No clear direction for the organization and mobilization of graduates, 4. Lack of provisions for training and seminars, and 5. Lack of Resources such as textbooks, modules, and reference books.

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Conclusion

1. Most of the PHEI in Tarlac Province doesn't have an orientation particularly about RA 9163 or the NSTP Act of 2001 before teaching NSTP.
2. Some institutions don't have planning, coaching, mentoring, and even seminars and trainings related to NSTP.
3. Topics such as good citizenship values, environmental management, drug education, personal development, disaster preparedness and awareness, and first aid are very important lessons that must be included in both the LTS and CWTS syllabus.
4. NSTP trainers experience various problems and challenges one of which is the lack of provisions for training and seminars resulting in limitation of NSTP topics that the students must need to know and practice. Also, the lack of administrative support and lack of proper allocation of funds can lead to a lack of facilities, equipment, and supplies that may be used in teaching. One respondent also stated that "lack of proper equipment makes teaching harder and if all survival skills will be taught theoretically, I don't know if that helps.

Recommendations

1. NSTP Director or coordinator may request a standard orientations and training for NSTP instructors or facilitators from the office of the civil defense, commission on higher education and any government agencies related to NSTP.
 2. School administration or NSTP directors should provide training or seminars related to NSTP for them to know what or which lessons should be taught in NSTP- LTS or CWTS.
 3. School administration may hire additional faculty for NSTP since some institution has only 1 faculty handling a huge number of students.
 4. Schools who taught First aid as part of NSTP subject should have a standardized qualification for hiring NSTP Faculty such as a certified first aider or have a background in medical field.
 5. The NSTP Director with the help of NSTP coordinator should conduct a monthly or quarterly monitoring and evaluation for NSTP faculty and NSTP activities.
 6. School administrators should support NSTP especially when it comes to the allocation of funds.
 7. NSTP Implementers and Directors should work on the creation of handbooks or modules to have standardized lessons in teaching NSTP.
 8. The NSTP Implementer with the help of NSTP Director and coordinator should provide a clear direction and instruction for the organization and mobilization of NSTP graduates.
 9. The NSTP unit/office with the help of school administrator should establish a memorandum of agreement between schools and communities for the deployment of NSTP graduates.
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10. The researcher also recommended conducting other research regarding this study.

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ROANN DOMINGO BANGIS, a 24-year-old and licensed professional teacher and a part-time review coach has been a full-time NSTP, non-military component Instructor at Tarlac State University for almost 3 years. During her first year of service, she was given the chance to be the assistant coordinator of Literacy Training Service. She is the one who plans activities in LTS together with the LTS coordinator to strengthen and develop the civic responsibilities of the students. She trained also in first aid and basic life support to strengthen her skills and knowledge in disaster preparedness. She was also a field area supervisor of DSWD last 2019 before she was became a university lecturer. Her

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